

RADiation harvesting of bioactive peptides from egg **prO**teins and their integration in ad**V**anced functional products

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DELIVERABLE REPORT

Exploitation Plan

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ABSTRACT

The RADOV Communication and Dissemination Plan has been developed within the overall RADOV Communication Strategy following the basic objectives drafted in the RADOV proposal. The procedures and tools to support communication and dissemination of RADOV scientific results are setup and functional. This Plan is an evolving document, which will be continuously updated to match emerging needs during the lifetime of the RADOV project.

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(1) Introduction

This document outlines the first version of the Exploitation Plan for the RADOV project. It drafts the strategy and the specific actions for the exploitation of results, as well as information about particular results, and the expectations of the partners on the exploitable results of the project. This report is divided into 6 sections. After the introduction and the description of the exploitation strategy, the report presents the preliminary key exploitable results as they have been identified and revised through the project to date. Then the assessment of IPR is provided.

This is the first version of the Exploitation Plan and it will be updated as the project progresses, with new versions in M24 and M45, based on what is learnt during the work.

1.1 Aims and objectives

The dissemination and exploitation of results are of great importance in RADOV, so a dedicated Work Package (WP5) has been created which focuses on the effective dissemination, exploitation and user uptake of project results. The Exploitation Plan developed within WP5 has the overall aim of maximising the impacts created by the project by facilitating the use of its outputs and findings.

The specific objectives of the Exploitation Plan are to:

- Outline expected exploitation procedures, plans and strategies;
- Summarise the strategy of beneficiaries and specific actions related to the protection and exploitation of project results;
- Present a clear vision of the intended impacts of the project and a well-planned strategy for the protection and exploitation of results.

The aims of exploitation activities are to create conditions for:

- Sustaining project outcomes after the funding period to influence future strategic planning of value chain businesses and policy;
- Maximising the exploitation potential of project activities, findings and outputs for economic, environmental and social benefits;
- Supporting the use and benefits from the outcomes during and beyond the project lifetime.

All Partners are committed to communicating and disseminating the results developed in the project and exploiting them directly or enabling their exploitation. The identified target groups of such activities are:

- a) the research community in the field of radiation processing
- b) large companies and SMEs from the radiation processing and egg product industries
- c) large companies and SMEs from the food, pharma, packaging, biotechnology and nutraceutical sectors
- d) public institutions and policy makers at national, European and worldwide level.

1.2 Rationale

The planning of exploitation activities, led by HUD, but with inputs from all partners, is a progressive, iterative process, co-developed with the stakeholders. All RADOV partners are involved in dissemination and exploitation in order to foster awareness and the transfer of results for the creation of impacts. Such impacts are expected to be in their own countries, communities and sectors, and in other countries that are otherwise not represented in the consortium. Of particular importance are the commercial partners, who may wish to directly exploit the results of the project. It is important that the IPR is controlled in such a way as to enable this, while meeting the requirements of the Grant Agreement.

(2) Exploitation: What must be done?

The RADOV GA requires each beneficiary to – up to four years after the end of the action - take measures aiming to ensure ‘exploitation’ of its results. This includes:

- (a) using them in further research activities;
- (b) developing, creating or marketing a product or process;
- (c) creating and providing a service;
- (d) using them in standardisation activities.

Each beneficiary must take measures aiming to ensure the exploitation of their results, either by themselves (e.g., for further research or for commercial or industrial exploitation in its own activities) or by others (other beneficiaries or third parties, e.g. through licensing or by transferring the ownership of results). Beneficiaries must be proactive and take specific measures to ensure that their results are used (to the extent possible and justified). However, exploitation does not necessarily need to be done directly by the participants. They are entitled to choose for that be done by another entity. Such indirect exploitation can be performed by licensing the results or assigning them to third parties as well as providing open access, in accordance with the requirements established in the grant agreement and the consortium agreement. In RADOV, all project partners are involved in dissemination and exploitation in order to foster and ensure awareness and transfer results for the highest possible impact.

(3) Exploitation Strategy in RADOV

Project exploitation has been carefully detailed starting from the very initial stages of project implementation, and is being reported in the Exploitation plan (i.e., preliminary, mid-term and final version of the Exploitation Plan – M12, M24, M45). It is also planned to hold a dedicated workshop to discuss all possible outcomes, which of these will need to be protected and how this will be done. This will add information to Table 1 for the updates of this deliverable.

Partners’ organizations will benefit in several ways from RADOV implementation as it represents a step further in the field of research related to nuclear technology and its applications in industrial and medical sectors (development of new e-beam irradiation protocols, identification of new raw materials from lateral streams of

current egg industry processes, identification of new fields of research related to nuclear technology, development of new added value products and applications that can boost many industries and develop new market segments). RADOV results, besides developing new applications for selected industries (food packaging and wound dressing) will represent a great starting point for new investigations on the use of ionising radiation (IR) in the medical sector (cancer research), agriculture (efficiency of green agricultural production, reduction of the use of pesticides and chemical fertilisers with impact on the environmental footprint) and climate change mitigation actions (wastewater treatment). This is the reason why the project consortium intends to disseminate its results on a large scale, enabling cross fertilization so as to be able to expand its impact, cement and further develop it, extending benefit to other sectors. To this extent, while some industrial processes will remain confidential for business convenience, the protocols developed for treating egg products with IR and the biological activities identified in the developed peptide and protein combinations will converge in a database, some of which will be open to research and industrial players who might be interested in investigating and developing new know-how on the basis of these results.

As input to the Exploitation plan (EP), market research will be conducted by experts at HUD and in other partners in order to ensure that the selected applications can have a significant relevant impact on market sectors and to identify further potential users. This will be supported by using industrial contacts in bodies with an interest in nuclear technologies, such as the International Irradiation Association (iiA), the IAEA and the H2020 Innovation Pilot project IFAST and by resources available from the EU. As well as selecting possible marketing routes, the market research will allow the size of the market and the competing technologies to be identified and a comparison with the RADOV technology made. This information, along with the IPR policy and the dissemination activities, will form the basis for the Exploitation Plan.

(4) Preliminary Plan for Key Exploitable Results

The first step for developing the appropriate and comprehensive Exploitation Plan was to identify the list of Key Exploitable Results (KERs) being developed in the RADOV project. An indicative set of generic questions were used to guide the thinking of what constitutes a key exploitable result:

- What exploitable results are the project participants hoping to generate?
- What forms, if relevant, can the exploitation of these results take (industrial use, patenting, technology transfer, publication, etc.)?
- What conditions will need to be fulfilled to enable exploitation of the results (cost of implementation and ease of obtaining)?
- What each participant is hoping to gain from the project? Are the expectations of all participants compatible and coherent?

Some examples of types of key exploitable results include:

- New technology;

- New technical/scientific/societal knowledge and data (in the form of software, new process, scientific result, evidence of successful pilot, new design, educational resource, evidence-based recommendation for action);
- New collaboration platform/mechanism.

An overview of the preliminary KER and their potential uses is given in Table 1.

Table 1: Key Exploitable Results

KER	Description	Target audience
1	Development of new irradiation processes to produce valuable peptides from egg proteins and egg products	Companies and SMEs from irradiation and egg products industry
2	Improved use of lateral streams and waste of egg industry	Companies and SMEs from irradiation and egg products industry
3	Demonstration of a new production method for bioactive peptide	Companies and SMEs from food, pharma, packaging, biotechnology, nutraceutical sectors
4	Novel hydrogel wound dressing	Companies and SMEs from pharma and biotechnology sectors
5	Novel active food packaging film	Companies and SMEs from Food and packaging sectors
6	Potential new antibiotic	Companies and SMEs from pharma and biotechnology sectors

This table will be updated throughout the duration of the project and, in particular, during the planned IPR workshop.

(5) Intellectual Property Rights

In addition to following the EU Open Access requirements, each beneficiary has an obligation to protect its results and must adequately protect them for an appropriate period and with appropriate territorial coverage. This is primarily if the results can reasonably be expected to be commercially or industrially exploited. When deciding on protection, the beneficiary must consider its own legitimate interests and the legitimate interests (especially commercial) of the other beneficiaries. Effective exploitation of the exploitable results depends upon, amongst other issues, the proper management of intellectual property, which should be part of the overall management of knowledge in the project. Throughout the RADOV project, specific actions have been, and will continue to be, undertaken for addressing the issues related to the intellectual property rights. These include the pre-existing knowledge (Background) of the project partners, an assessment of the results generated during the project, proposals for the optimal protection of IPR, and ownership and proper implementation of IPR protection measures.

The framework of the IPR management is set out within the Consortium Agreement, which stipulates the rules related to the following IP issues:

- Identification of the Background and the specific limitations and conditions for its implementation;
- Ownership of the results;
- Transfer of the results;
- Access rights to the Background and the results;
- Non-disclosure of the information.

5.1. Protection of results

Participants will assess the possibility of protecting their results once these are generated. Beneficiaries are free to choose any available form of protection of intellectual property. Standard forms of protection which will be considered include patent, trademark, industrial design, copyright, trade-secret, confidentiality agreement. The choice of the most suitable form of IP protection, as well as the duration and geographical coverage, depends upon the results (e.g. if it is an invention, software or a database), and the business plans for their exploitation and legitimate interests of consortium partners. Although not mandatory for one organisation to inform other partners about actions to protect Intellectual Property, it is considered good practice to consult before deciding whether to protect results, particularly if dealing with potentially joint Intellectual Property. Examples of the protection of Intellectual Property are listed in Table 2.

Table 2 - Examples of the protection of Intellectual Property according to the type of result

Subject matter	Patent	Utility model	New design	Copyright	Trade mark	Confidential information
Invention	x	x				
Software	x			x		
Scientific article				x		
Design of a product			x	x	x	
Name of a product/service/project					x	
Know-how						x
Website			x	x	x	

Although the protection of Intellectual Property is vital for a prospective commercial or industrial exploitation, it is not always mandatory. No protection is necessary if: i) it is impossible under EU or national law; ii) not justified in view of the (potential) commercial or industrial exploitation; or iii) not required by the action’s objective and other relevant elements, such as potential markets and countries in which competitors are located, whether or not the additional protection of a part of a certain technology would bring significantly broader protection.

(6) Conclusions

The aim of this deliverable is to provide a first version of the Exploitation Plan for the results of the RADOV project. Deliverable D5.4 is a first assessment of the preliminary

key exploitable results and of the ways and modes of how the consortium intends to prepare for creating the post-project legacy. This will be by use of the results, or promoting the results, for use by stakeholders and other actors outside the consortium, and thereby creating impacts.

The preparation for exploitation is an iterative process that comes to the fore when project results are emerging. The Exploitation plan will be updated as the project completes its final stages to ensure dynamic and successful exploitation of project results, avoid infringement of Intellectual Property Rights and mitigate risks that could endanger the exploitation of results.

HUD will continue to secure the involvement of all project partners in exploitation activities, guide them through the process and encourage them to contribute to the exploitation.

D5.4 will be followed by an updated Exploitation Plan in M24 and a final Plan in M45. The iterative process during the remainder of the project will use the dedicated workshop and sessions of partner meetings which are dedicated to exploitation which will lead to the updated Plans. This will include reviewing, updating and finalising the KERs, the overall project and partner level exploitation strategies and plans, and a detailed assessment of potential exploitation impacts.